

Studies on some Less Familiar Ferrocyanogen Complexes. Part V. Interactions of Be(II) and Cr(III) with Potassium Ferro- and Ferricyanides at 80° and their Composition by Amperometry

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Dilute solutions of beryllium nitrate and chromic chloride do not interact with potassium ferrocyanide at the ordinary temperature to form insoluble complexes. These, however, react at higher temperatures. The reactions have been studied at 80° employing the mercury pool as the reference electrode and potassium chlorate as the supporting electrolyte. Titrations between beryllium nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide have been carried out at 80°. Evidence for the formation of the complex $K_2Be_3 II (Fe^{II} Cy_6)_2$ has been obtained.

Conductometric and potentiometric titrations between chromic chloride and potassium ferrocyanide do not give satisfactory results, but the amperometric titrations, carried out at 80°, give evidence for the formation of the complex $KCr^{III}Fe^{II}Cy_6$. Amperometric studies, carried out under similar conditions, give evidence for the formation of the complex $Cr^{III}Fe^{III}Cy_6$ by the interaction of chromic chloride and potassium ferricyanide at 80°.

Amongst the metal ferrocyanogen complexes, beryllium and chromic compounds differ from other compounds of this class in as much as that their formation is favoured by high temperatures. As already reported in Part IV (this issue, p. 293) the reaction between beryllium chloride and potassium ferrocyanide took place at the room temperature only with the concentrated solutions of the reactants, whereas with the dilute solutions, a higher temperature (60-80°) was needed for its completion. Also in a previous communication (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18B, 643) it was reported that besides the formation of a soluble complex at the room temperature, the reaction between chromic chloride and potassium ferrocyanide, when carried out at a higher temperature (80°), resulted in the formation of a precipitate, highly gelatinous in character. Elucidation of the composition of both these complexes, employing physical methods, presented a number of difficulties.

Since the amperometric titrations offer a neat method for studying complex-ion formation with fairly dilute solutions, it was chosen for studying the composition of beryllium ferrocyanide. The investigations, however, presented many experimental difficulties. Firstly the beryllium chloride solution could not be used; secondly a suitable supporting electrolyte was to be found out because we failed to get a wave as reported in the literature (Kemula and Michalski, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1933, 5, 436) with beryllium nitrate alone; and finally a suitable reference electrode had to be selected to replace the calomel electrode (found unsuitable for working at 80°). The beryllium nitrate—potassium ferrocyanide reaction was therefore studied in detail with two aspects in view, viz., (i) polarographic investigation of beryllium nitrate and (ii) elucidation of the composition of beryllium ferrocyanide with the help of amperometric titrations.

The chromic chloride—potassium ferrocyanide reaction was first studied by employing potentiometric and conductometric titrations. Potentiometric titrations carried out at 80°, employing a $FeCy_6^{4-} \rightleftharpoons FeCy_6^{3-} + e$ couple at the platinum electrode, failed to provide sharp breaks in the titration curves, thereby furnishing little information regarding the composition of the complex. Although the conductometric titration method tried could supply some information regarding the composition of chromic ferrocyanide, it had its own

limitations. One factor mainly responsible for the limited applicability of the method in this particular case was the appreciable decrease in the mobility of the ions in the reaction mixture due to the highly gelatinous nature of the reaction product. The results on the preliminary experiments on conductometry at $80 \pm 0.1^\circ$ at one particular concentration are given below.

0.5M-CrCl ₃ in the cell.	0.5M-K ₄ FeCy ₆ from the curve.	Ratio at the point of inflection. C ₃₊ : FeCy ₆ ⁴⁻ .
10 c.c.	9.8 c.c., 15.9 c.c.	1:1; 1:1.5
0.5M-K ₄ FeCy ₆ in the cell.	0.1M-CrCl ₃ from the curve.	
10 c.c.	5.1 c.c., 21.2 c.c.	1:10; 1:2.4

From the above it is evident that only the titrations carried out with CrCl₃ in the cell gave results of some importance (and that too in one stray case). On this basis the complex chromic ferrocyanide would have the probable formula KCrFeCy₆ and KCrFeCy₆·0.5K₄FeCy₆ (an adsorption complex). Since fantastic results were obtained for the reverse titrations, in spite of the fact that typical titration curves were obtained, it was thought worthwhile to use a more suitable and at the same time accurate physical method for finding out its composition. The amperometric method was therefore also employed in these investigations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Beryllium nitrate solution was prepared by diluting A.R. sample in about 250c.c. of water and its strength, determined gravimetrically after weighing as BeO, was found to be 0.54M. Chromic chloride (A.R.) was dissolved in double distilled water and its strength was determined iodometrically (W.Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 1945, Vol. I, p. 288) after oxidising the solution to chromate by sodium peroxide. Potassium ferrocyanide and potassium ferricyanide (recrystallised) were also dissolved in double distilled water and the strength determined volumetrically. Concentrated solutions of potassium ferro- and ferricyanides were kept stored in dark bottles.

Polarographic Measurements

Fischer electrode in conjunction with a Multiflex galvanometer (Type MGF2) was employed for measurement of the current. The electrodes used were the dropping mercury electrode, S.C.E. (Fibre and dip types), and the mercury pool. Nitrogen gas, purified after passing through chromous chloride and pyrogallol, was used for maintaining the inert atmosphere. Thermostatic oil bath at $80 \pm 0.1^\circ$ was used for temperature control. For studying the chromic chloride—potassium ferrocyanide reaction, potassium chloride was used as the supporting electrolyte and gelatin (0.01%) as the maximum suppressor.

Amperometric Titrations

Before carrying out the amperometric titrations between beryllium nitrate and potassium ferrocyanide, a number of polarograms of beryllium nitrate solutions in different supporting electrolytes (saturated CaCl₂; CaCl₂ saturated in 0.1M-HCl; KClO₄ in 0.1M-HCl; 0.1M KClO₄) and maximum suppressors (0.01% methyl red; 0.01% gelatin) employing S. C. E. (Fibre and dip types) as well as the mercury pool as reference electrodes were drawn. No waves were obtained with Be(NO₃)₂ solution without supporting electrolyte. From the different polarograms studied, it was found that the most suitable condition

for performing amperometric titrations was to apply a potential of about 1.90 volts at the dropping mercury electrode, using the mercury pool as the other half element with gelatin (0.01%) as the maximum suppressor and 0.1M-KClO₃ as the supporting electrolyte. Titrations were performed with Be(NO₃)₂ in the cell (direct) as well as K₄FeCy₆ in the cell (reverse). Since in the direct titrations the current went on continuously increasing, it was difficult to locate the null point; only one set of readings was taken. Better results were, however, obtained with the reverse titrations. The electrolyte solution was diluted to 20c.c. with potassium chlorate solution and 1c.c. of gelatin.

For studying the reaction between chromic chloride and potassium ferrocyanide, a polarogram of chromic chloride (using dip type S.C.E.) was taken. 0.1M-Chromic chloride (1c.c.) was taken in the cell and the total volume was made to 20c.c. with 1c.c. of gelatin solution and the rest, supporting electrolyte. The polarogram showed one irreversible wave (the second wave could not be realised since a hydrogen wave due to the hydrolysis of chromic ions was obtained in the vicinity of 1.4 volts) with $E_{\frac{1}{2}}=0.88$ volt. A potential of 1.0 volt was chosen for the titrations. Both direct (CrCl₃ in the cell) and the reverse (K₄FeCy₆ in the cell) titrations were tried. In the reverse titrations the current increased continuously on the addition of chromic chloride and the equivalence point could not be successfully located.

The amperometric titrations between chromic chloride and potassium ferricyanide were carried out at two different potentials. The direct titrations were carried out at 1.0 volt, whereas the reverse titrations were done at 0.0 volt (since in the case of potassium ferricyanide $E_{\frac{1}{2}} = \pm 0.2$ V, and a diffusion current for all negative values of the potential applied). Reverse titrations after applying a potential of 1.0 volt could not be satisfactorily performed due to the residual current.

The results are summarised in the following tables and typical curves are depicted in Figs. 1 to 3.

TABLE I

Potential applied = 1.85 volts. Temp. = 80 ± 0.1°.

Vol. in the cell.	Direct titrations. Vol. from the curve.	Ratio at the point of inflection.
0.154 M-Be(NO ₃) ₂	0.1 M-K ₄ FeCy ₆	Be ²⁺ : FeCy ₆ ⁴⁻
0.6 c.c.	2.4 c.c.	1:2.6
	Reverse titrations.	
0.1M-K ₄ FeCy ₆	0.1M-Be(NO ₃) ₂	
0.2 c.c.	0.2 c.c.	3:2
0.4	0.4	3:2
0.6	0.6	3:2

TABLE II

Potential applied = 1.0 volt. Temp. = 80 ± 0.1°.

Vol. in the cell.	Vol. from the curve.	Ratio at the point of inflection.
0.1M-CrCl ₃	0.1M-K ₄ FeCy ₆	Cr ³⁺ : FeCy ₆ ⁴⁻
0.6 c.c.	0.60 c.c.	1:1
0.8	0.80	1:1
1.0	0.95	1:1

TABLE III

Vol. in the cell, 0.1M-CrCl ₃	Vol. from the curve, 0.1M-K ₃ FeCy ₆	Ratio at the point of inflection, Cr ³⁺ : FeCy ₆ ³⁻
	Potential applied=1.0 volt. Temp.=90±0.1°.	
0.6 c.c.	0.40 c.c.	1.5 : 1
0.8	0.60	1.3 : 1
1.0	0.75	1.3 : 1
0.1M-K ₃ FeCy ₆	0.1M-CrCl ₃ .	
	Potential applied=0.0 volt. Temp.=80±0.1°.	
0.4	0.4	1 : 1
0.6	0.6	1 : 1
1.0	0.8	1.1 : 1

DISCUSSION

Amperometric titrations with beryllium nitrate in the cell did not provide typical amperometric curves. Here the current went on increasing due to hydrolysis. The probable equivalence point, however, gave a ratio of Be²⁺ : FeCy₆⁴⁻ as 1:2.6, showing thereby the great adsorptive capacity of the complex K₂Be^{II}Fe^{II}Cy₆ for the ferrocyanide ions. The results support the earlier work (Part IV) where the existence of adsorption complexes like K₂Be^{II}Fe^{II}Cy₆. K₄FeCy₆ was envisaged on the basis of direct conductometric titrations.

The reverse titrations, potassium ferrocyanide in the cell, gave the ratio Be²⁺ : FeCy₆⁴⁻ as 3:2, thereby indicating the formation of the complex K₃Be^{II}(Fe^{II}Cy₆)₂. Further, the amperometric titrations were of extra advantage in as so far as they could supply information regarding the composition of the compound formed when beryllium nitrate is added to potassium ferrocyanide—a fact which could be investigated on the basis of conductometric titrations.

FIG. 1. Curves 1-0.2 c.c. 2-0.4 c.c. and 3-0.6 c.c. of 0.1 M-K₃FeCy₆ in the cell.

FIG. 2. Curves 1-0.6 c.c., 2-0.8 c.c., and 3-1.0 c.c. of $M-CrCl_3$ in the cell.

Summing up the studies on the composition of beryllium ferrocyanide, it may be said that the complex has got the composition $K_2Be^{II}Fe^{II}Cy_6$ and $K_2Be_3^{II}(Fe^{II}Cy_6)_2$, depending on the mode of mixing the reactants. When potassium ferrocyanide is added to beryllium, a compound with the formula $K_2Be^{II}Fe^{II}Cy_6$ is obtained, whereas on adding beryllium nitrate to potassium ferrocyanide, a complex having the formula $K_2Be_3(Fe^{II}Cy_6)_2$ is formed. Moreover, the compound $K_2BeFeCy_6$ shows a great tendency to adsorb the ferrocyanide ions and hence under these conditions the reaction cannot be employed for the estimation of beryllium, as reported recently (Part IV, *loc. cit.*).

Chromic Ferro-and Ferricyanide Complexes

The results on amperometric titrations between chromic chloride and potassium ferro-and ferricyanide solutions provide ample proof regarding the composition of the precipitates obtained by their interaction at 80° . As already pointed out, the potentiometric and conductometric titration methods failed to supply the required information about their composition.

The curves for the direct titrations between chromic chloride and potassium ferrocyanide are typical in nature. Initially the current goes on decreasing with the removal of chromic ions due to the precipitation of chromic ferrocyanide, but after complete precipitation the current is almost constant in view of the nonreducibility of potassium ferrocyanide at the dropping mercury electrode. The ratio 1:1 for the reactants found on the basis of these titrations would point towards the composition $KCr^{III}Fe^{II}Cy_6$ for the complex.

The amperometric titrations carried out between chromic chloride and potassium ferricyanide at 1.0 volt gave ratios $Cr^{3+} : FeCy_6^{3-}$ as 1.3:1 and 1.5:1. Such ratios although do not provide any precise information regarding the composition of chromic ferricyanide, it may be said that a compound having the composition $Cr^{III}Fe^{III}Cy_6$ is formed with chromic ions adsorbed on it. The reverse titration proved, however more fruitful and gave a ratio 1:1 for the reactants. An interesting point regarding the shape of the amperometric

titration curves in this case is worth mentioning. It was found that the current values became negative with successive addition of chromic chloride from the burette to potassium ferricyanide solution. In order to explain this behaviour one has to take into consideration the hydrolytic nature of the complex. It is quite probable that chromic ferricyanide hydrolyses to yield chromic hydroxide and the negative current may be due to some of the hydroxyl ions present in the reaction mixture. Separate experiments performed with buffers (pH 8) and alkali solutions gave negative current at 0.0. volt.

FIG. 3. Curves 1-0.6 c.c., 2-0.8 c.c. and 3-1.0 c.c. of $0.1 M-CrCl_3$ in the cell.

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